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Turning climate-related information into added value for traditional **MEDiterraneanGrape**, **OLive** and **Durum** wheat food systems

Deliverable 6.23

Summary of Dissemination and Communication Activities n.3

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The MED-GOLD project aims to demonstrate the proof-of-concept on how climate services can make European agriculture and food systems more competitive, resilient and efficient through three case studies in the olive, grape and durum wheat sectors.

The dissemination and communication work tries to maximize the impact of the project's results through different channels and target audiences, as is described in the MED-GOLD deliverable D7.1 "Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Management Plan" [RD.1]. This deliverable synthesises all the communication and dissemination activities performed during the period M25-M36 towards the following objectives:

- Increase of website visitors
- Estimate the impact on social media channel.
- Engage the participation in dissemination activities such as webinars or living Lab
- Increase the ratio between number of publications published vs. publications under revision
- Maintain the number of communication material by period (infosheet, newsletter)
- Open the MED-GOLD video channel
- Quick adaptation to external changes (case summer school transformed to Living Lab)
- Improvements in the multilanguage communication in website and social media channels
- Increase the number of definitions in the multilanguage glossary
- Increase the support of external websites and social media
- Increase the visualisations of media material hosted in the website.

1. OBJECTIVES

A comprehensive and common strategy on communication, dissemination and exploitation of the MED-GOLD project is required for a wide adoption of the project by the different target audiences. The work performed during the period M25-M36 keeps the processes followed in the previous periods, while it reinforces and discusses aspects related to multilanguage information, policy briefs and dissemination activities. The objective of this document is to describe in a simple way the different activities performed during this period and to analyse the results based on external tools such as Google analytics, Twitter Analytics and Wayback Machine

- The main purpose of this document is to describe and analyse all activities and tasks developed in the context of the Dissemination and Communication as well as the results of the different tasks. In the same line, a comparison between the current period and the past periods will show the advances and improvements in the strategies adopted by the consortium and redefine this strategy in case of unsatisfactory results.
- As established in the MED-GOLD grant agreement, this document will collect and describe all the contributions and advances aimed at the dissemination of the MED-GOLD project.
- The scope of this deliverable is to present a yearly report related to dissemination and communication activities performed by the consortium through the collection of data, reports, activities etc. that describe such activities.
- The analysis of the behaviour of both social media and website will be performed using tools like twitter analytics and google analytics. To ensure that all communication and dissemination activities have been properly logged, this document employs the procedure described in deliverable D7.1 "Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Management Plan [RD.1] and MED-GOLD Quality Plan [RD.2]. In this way, all the activities were centralised in a spreadsheet that forms the basis of this report following the structure of the deliverable 6.7 "Summary of Dissemination and Communication Activities N.1" [RD.3] and 6.22 "Summary of Dissemination and Communication Activities N.1" [RD.4] This document could be considered as an update that includes the progress in C&D activities.

With this deliverable, the project has contributed to the achievement of the following objectives (DOA, PartBTable1.1):

No.	Objective	Yes
1	To co-design, co-develop, test, and assess the added value of proof-of-concept climate services for olive, grape, and durum wheat	
2	To refine, validate, and upscale the three pilot services with the wider European and global user communities for olive, grape, and durum wheat	
3	To ensure replicability of MED-GOLD climate services in other crops/climates (e.g., coffee) and to establish links to policy making globally	
4	To implement a comprehensive communication and commercialization plan for MED-GOLD climate services to enhance market uptake	
5	To build better informed and connected end-user communities for the global olive oil, wine, and pasta food systems and related policy making	X

2. IMPACT

Some of the objectives and tasks established in the MED-GOLD Grant Agreement [RD.5] related to communication and dissemination have been collected in the activities performed by Workpackage 6 “*Communication and exploitation of the MED-GOLD value chain*”. The third period continues with the process adopted and clearly defined in D7.1, MED-GOLD Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Management Plan” [RD.1].

From a practical point of view, the third period can be seen as the consolidation of the process adopted previously in terms of communication and dissemination; the results obtained during the period reported in this deliverable indicate an increase in participants, website visitors, social media users, webinar attendees, etc.

Taking into consideration the conclusions of the D.22 [RD.4], the objectives of this period also focus on increase the impact of the MED-GOLD project as a reference in the Climate Services.

No.	Expected impact	Yes
1	Providing added-value for the decision-making process addressed by the project, in terms of effectiveness, value creation, optimised opportunities and minimised risk	
2	Enhancing the potential for market uptake of climate services demonstrated by addressing the added value	
3	Ensuring the replicability of the methodological frameworks for value added climate services in potential end-user markets	
4	To implement a comprehensive communication and commercialization plan for MED-GOLD climate services to enhance market uptake	
5	To build better informed and connected end-user communities for the global olive oil, wine, and pasta food systems and related policy making	This document collect and analyse all the activities developed by WP6 during the last period. In this sense, the outcomes will be used to improve the methodologies and strategies adopted to disseminate and communicate the project.

3. DEFINITIONS

Concepts and terms used in this document and needing a definition are included in the following table:

Concept / Term	Definition
Bounce Rate	Percentage of visitors that leave a webpage without taking an action, such as clicking on a link, filling out a form, or making a purchase.
Frontend	Is the practice of converting data to a graphical interface, through the use of HTML, CSS, and JavaScript, so that users can view and interact with that data.
Backend	Refers to parts of a computer application or a program's code that allow it to operate and that cannot be accessed by a user.

4. ACRONYMS

Acronyms used in this document and needing a definition are included in the following table:

Acronym	Definition
C&D	Communication and Dissemination
EN	English
ES	Spanish
FR	French
GR	Greek
IT	Italian
PT	Portuguese
GA	General Assembly

5. REFERENCES

The following documents, although not part of this document, amplify or clarify its contents. Reference documents are those not applicable and referenced within this document. They are referenced in this document in the form [RD.x]:

Ref.	Title	Code	Version	Date
[RD.1]	Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Management Plan	D7.1	2.1	30/05/2019
[RD.2]	MED-GOLD Quality Plan		1.3	23/04/2018
[RD.3]	Summary of Dissemination and Communication Activities N.1	D6.7	1.2	30/05/2019
[RD.4]	Summary of Dissemination and Communication Activities N.2	D6.22	1.4	20/11/2019
[RD.5]	MED-GOLD Grant Agreement			16/10/2017
[RD.6]	MED-GOLD GA Minutes			31/10/2019
[RD.7]	Build Your Author Platform: A Literary Agent's Guide to Growing Your Audience in 14 Steps			13/05/2014
[RD.8]	Report on the MED-GOLD mailing list			26/06/2018
[RD.9]	Second Feedback report from users on olive oil pilot service development	D2.7		31/05/2020
[RD.10]	Second Feedback report from users on wine pilot service development	D3.7		31/05/2020
[RD.11]	Second Feedback report from users on durum wheat pilot service development	D4.7		31/05/2020
[RD.12]	Science-based knowledge relevant for Climate related Policies n.2	D6.17		30/11/2020

6. COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION CHANNELS

The main channels adopted by MED-GOLD serve as way to communicate the activities, outcomes and news related to the project to the external audience. It turned out that the website and the twitter account are the most important and effective tools to reach the objective established in the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Management Plan [RD.1]. The dissemination activities are oriented to communicate using a specific language and concepts related to the objectives of MED-GOLD. Different ways to reach this goal have been created since the beginning of the project.

In this report, the communication activities are described in sections 6.3.1 to 6.3.8 followed by dissemination activities described in sections 6.3.9 to 6.3.13. The section 6.3.14 provides information in relation to policy community.

6.1. STATE OF THE ART

Dissemination and communication of results plays a central role in European research and innovation projects. In the frame of workpackage 6, various activities have been developed to meet this goal.

Currently some results show an important advance in meeting the majority of objectives planted in the beginning of MED-GOLD.

Table 6.1 lists the overview during the life of the project in terms of Communication and Dissemination. In the following chapters, an analysis and particular description will be shown for each activity carried out during the reported period (November 2019 - October 2020).

Table 6-1 State of the art along the project life

STATE OF THE ART	Total
MED-GOLD WEBSITE	
Website Users	6090
Website Sessions	10806
MED-GOLD SOCIAL NETWORKS	
Twitter impressions	216852
Twitter engagements	4025
Twitter retweets	580
Twitter likes	1156
Twitter media views	714
Twitterurl clicks	739
Twitter engagement rate	13
MED-GOLD MAILING LISTS	
Total number of members	170
Academic Network	35
MED-GOLD NEWSLETTERS	
Total number of published Newsletter	4
MED-GOLD EVENTS	
Participation in conferences	26
Workshops	5
INTERACTION WITH OTHER INITIATIVES	
Initiative Related To Climate Services	14
Agriculture Services	10
Potential Initiatives Contacted	26

STATE OF THE ART	Total
EXTERNAL COMMUNICATION CHANNELS	
News	60
Podcast	4
Press release	24
Social media references	30
External Video Channel appearances	5
MED-GOLD YouTube Channel videos published	10
External website	121
DISSEMINATION CHANNELS	
MED-GOLD Living Lab	1
MED-GOLD Infosheet	6
MED-GOLD Webinar	2
MED-GOLD Forum Discussions	31
MED-GOLD Publications	
Published Papers	8
Article Under review	2
Abstracts Submitted	11
CONTACT WITH THE POLICY COMMUNITY	
Contacted members	12

6.2. METHODS

The following methods and analysis were applied to determine the results obtained during the reported period:

- Increasing rates: comparison between results obtained in the previously reported period (P1 – Nov 2018 – Nov 2019) and current reported period (P2)
- Direct measuring: direct data taken from spreadsheets updated by each partner involved in WP6
- Website and social media analysis: analysis performed using external reports, such as Google Analytics and Twitter Analytics
- Indirect measuring: qualitative and quantitative estimation concluded from correlated or indirect information like number of visits, number of clicks, and traffic deviation, activity calls, etc.

6.3. MAIN RESULTS

The varioust activities performed along the period reported in this document will be described in the following paragraphs. Each activity will show the main results obtained through different analysis using internal information (spreadsheets and databases) and external sources.

6.3.1. MED-GOLD WEBSITE

The MED-GOLD website (<https://www.med-gold.eu/>) in terms of *frontend* has not undergone modifications during the last period. The content (*backend*) has been strongly increased in compliance with the second General Assembly (2019), during which the consortium expressed the need to improve some aspects, especially the ones related to the Glossary and multilanguage content.

Figure 6.1 presents the variations performed on the frontend website since its publication. This information is based on periodic screenshots and confirm the consolidation of the current MED-GOLD website and shows the last two periods as a logical evolutions until the final version of the website. Figure 6.2 shows the initial and the most recent version of the MED-GOLD homepage.

Figure 6-1: Annual Frontend evolution

Figure 6-2: Frontend significant change performed between Nov-2019 (left) and Oct-2020 (right)

6.3.1.1. MULTILANGUAGE VERSIONS EVOLUTION

After the MED-GOLD website consolidation, the content of the website multilanguage version has been enriched in order to spread the MED-GOLD position focused to the general public; all the website content has been translated into the project languages (EN, IT, ES, PT, GR, FR).

The translation teams, as defined by the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Management Plan [RD.1], carried out the translation.

Internally each translation team member performed the assigned task and then the last version was revised before being uploaded to the website.

The tasks showed in the Table 6.2 were performed as part of the Multilanguage website content, except from those related to glossary that will be described in the next chapter. A total of 12 calls to translate the content in the MED-GOLD website have been made during the last period and each of one involves different sections of the web site.

Table 6-2 Multilanguage MED-GOLD Website Activities

Month	Task
oct-19	MED-GOLD Publications infosheet
nov-19	MED-GOLD Community website tab
nov-19	MED-GOLD Publications infosheet
nov-19	MED-GOLD News on the workshop
dic-19	MEDGOLD- Past Events
feb-20	MED-GOLD Summer School Announcement
mar-20	MED-GOLD Announcement WEBINAR on time scales.
mar-20	MED-GOLD vs coronavirus
mar-20	MED-GOLD News on Meet our External Advisory Board
abr-20	MED-GOLD News on Meet our External Advisory Board
abr-20	MED-GOLD Living - Lab
oct-20	MED-GOLD Publications infosheet

6.3.1.2. GLOSSARY CONTENT ACTIVITIES

The glossary section was a topic discussed in the second General Assembly (Oct-2019) in the frame of strategies to engage members and reinforce the MED-GOLD community [RD.6]. During the last period, the workpackage 6 started the activities focused on the glossary content, which were performed in different stages: revision, discussion, scope of the definitions, revision, translation, final revision, publication. The Figure 6-3 depicts the glossary content evolution during the last period, Nov 2019 to Oct 2020.

Figure 6-3: Published Glossary content

Forty five (45) definitions have been involved in the process as fundamental part of the strategies described in the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Management Plan. In compliance with the last General Assembly (2020) the activities concerning the glossary will have been performed until the end of the project with the objective to increase the number of keywords and definitions.

Figure 6-4 shows an example of the glossary in Greek language.

B

Βασική κλιματική μεταβλητή (Essential Climate Variable, ECV)

Μια βασική κλιματική μεταβλητή είναι μια φυσική, χημική ή βιολογική μεταβλητή ή μια ομάδα συνδεδεμένων μεταβλητών που συμβάλλει αποφασιστικά στον χαρακτηρισμό του κλίματος της Γης. Σε αυτές περιλαμβάνονται η βροχοπτώση, η θερμοκρασία και η πίεση, μεταξύ πολλών άλλων.

+ Bias correction

+ Βιοκλιματικές μεταβλητές

+ Βραχυπρόθεσμα

Figure 6-4: Multilanguage glossary (Greece)

6.3.2. WEBSITE IMPACT AND USERS

The website is a fundamental part in the strategy of the Dissemination and Communication of MED-GOLD. One of the conclusions in the Summary of Dissemination and Communication Activities N.2 [RD.4] indicates the need to increase the MED-GOLD impact through the content generated.

In this chapter, an analysis focused on the website activity in terms of traffic as an indirect technique to estimate the impact will be presented using information provided by *google analytics*.

Figure 6.5 depicts the comparison in the numbers of users who interacted with the MED-GOLD website on a monthly basis between M25 – M36. The curve of the graph shows a clear increase in the number of users compared to the previous period. It is important to highlight the constant behaviour during the first 5 months of this third period, reaching an average of 322 users as well as the increase of users in April 2020 coinciding both with the Webinar (What are the time scales of climate services for agriculture?) and the Living Lab promo campaign. An interesting behaviour linked with vacation period and the General Assembly month can be observed from August to October. This is due to a sectorial workshop (in person) conducted during the second General Assembly 2019. However the organisation of an in person workshop was not possible this year (2020) because of Covid-19 crisis.

Figure 6-5: MED-GOLD website user activity.

Table 6.3 summarizes the most important aspects related to the MED-GOLD website audience, demonstrating that the activities developed by the consortium have reached some of the objectives described in the previous report [RD.4].

Table 6-3 MED-GOLD website audience

Audience Activity	Current period	Last Period	Grow Rate
Users	3686	2785	32%
New Users	3632	2786	30%
Sessions	6613	4636	43%
Page Views	16101	11445	40.68%
Bounce Rate	61.18%	58.65%	4.32%
Average Session Duration	0:02:43	0:02:32	7.27%
Number of sessions per user	1.79	1.66	7.78%
Pages/Session	2.43	2.47	-1.38%

According to the website analysis, the distribution of users by countries shows that the European countries, particularly the Mediterranean countries, have interacted actively with the MED-GOLD website (Fig. 6.6). The map shows worldwide interactions (except from central Africa and some countries in Asia). Below will be explained in detail what this activity means in qualitative terms.

Figure 6-6: MED-GOLD website user world interaction.

Table 6-4 shows the top ten countries when comparing the behaviour between P2 (01-Nov-2019 to 31-Oct-2020) and the previously reported period in the D6.22 (Nov- 2018- Oct-2019). It shows a particularity related to new users and bounce rate that reinforce the idea that the real interest is focused on the Mediterranean countries.

Although USA and Australia show an interesting number of users accessing the MED-GOLD website, the rate bounce depicts that users do not take time exploring the website and probably they were looking for another kind of information. In the case of European countries, especially Mediterranean countries where the three sectorial partners have presence the behaviour is relevant.

In terms of quality of interactions, for example, Spain had 332 new users during this reported period, the duration per session was higher than in other countries and the bounce rate was lower compared with the rest of countries. This implies that the users connected from Spain knew in advance the kind of information provided by the website. A similar behaviour has been recorded for Portugal and Italy followed by Greece and France. This result matches the effort performed during the last period focused on translations tasks.

Table 6-4 MED-GOLD website comparison P2 vs P1

Country	Date Range	Users	New Users	Sessions	Bounce Rate	Pages/Session	Avg. Session Duration
Italy	P2	838	807	1861	0.54	2.79	234.26
Italy	P1	397	394	963	0.47	3.00	206.45
United States	P2	484	482	518	0.95	1.10	12.67
United States	P1	573	573	584	0.95	1.15	9.68
Spain	P2	345	332	993	0.46	3.30	240.98
Spain	P1	153	153	468	0.39	3.34	257.90
Greece	P2	190	187	273	0.63	2.37	98.78
Greece	P1	101	101	181	0.50	2.44	130.46
United Kingdom	P2	168	162	262	0.60	2.10	147.12
United Kingdom	P1	116	116	170	0.46	2.73	147.95
Portugal	P2	135	127	367	0.51	3.10	224.06
Portugal	P1	163	163	289	0.55	2.79	176.45
France	P2	113	111	154	0.66	2.16	116.66
France	P1	39	37	57	0.60	2.00	102.02
Netherlands	P2	79	79	89	0.67	1.90	31.38
Netherlands	P1	12	12	13	0.54	1.85	9.54
Germany	P2	69	68	125	0.68	1.90	79.86
Germany	P1	34	34	35	0.66	1.97	155.54
Australia	P2	59	59	78	0.82	1.35	46.14
Australia	P1	18	17	23	0.43	3.04	226.83

Taking as reference the *bounce rate*, the session was recalculated (Fig. 6.7) to define a “real” number of sessions. This overcome shows the relevance of the three sectors (Grape/Wine, Olive/Oil, Durum Wheat/Pasta).

Figure 6.8 presents the number of sessions (over 150) per country, as well as the number of users, new users and bounce rate. The impact of MED-GOLD is higher in the Mediterranean region and the United Kingdom, as can be seen in the map which denotes the influence of the participant countries in the MED-GOLD project.

Figure 6-7: MED-GOLD Recalculated Sessions in European Countries.

Figure 6-8: MED-GOLD website Mediterranean countries interaction.

According to “google analytics” during the period between 01-Nov-2019 and 27-Oct-2020 (P2) 43% of the interactions originated directly from the website, 36% from Organic search, 11% from social media (Twitter) and 10% referral from external websites. Figure 6-9 shows the comparison by absolute number between present period (P2) and the previous periods (PP) comprehend since the begin of the website and untill month 24 (31-Oct-2019). In all cases, the direct access to MED-GOLD has been the main way to interact with the website. During the P2, the number of interactions to MED-GOLD website through organic search had an increase compared with the previous period. This increase can be attributed to the campaign launched to promo the MED-GOLD summer School (MED-GOLD Living Lab) and the webinar “Timescales of Climate Services for Agriculture” using external websites and social media accounts.

Figure 6-9: Comparison between P2 and all previous periods (PP) in MED-GOLD website Acquisition Traffic

Another important point connected to the MED-GOLD website audience is related to social aspects. According to google analytics report, MED-GOLD website records can be considered equally distributed in terms of age and gender. Figure 6.10 shows the audience distribution by age and gender considering the 100% of sessions.

Figure 6-10: MED-GOLD Website audience

6.3.3.MED-GOLD SOCIAL NETWORKS

As was described in the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Management Plan [RD1], Twitter is an excellent choice of social media platform as it has a broad usability and is very readily accessible through several devices.

During the period reported (P2) the activity in the Twitter account measured in terms of total *cumulated impressions* and *total cumulated engagement* was 101545 and 1650 respectively. This outcome is positive considering that the MED-GOLD Twitter account is focused on a particular user profile.

Observing in detail the behaviour of this social media account, a punctual activity or event reach more impact on the users, for instance Webinar, MED-GOLD living Lab or the General Assembly. Figure 6.11 shows the monthly comparison since the last reported period; the peaks coincide with the launch of some MED-GOLD activities. In general, the trend is ascendant during the project. During August and September, the impact is lower mainly due to holiday period.

Figure 6-11: Monthly MED-GOLD Twitter Performance – Impressions (upper) Engagements (lower)

As was mentioned in the previous chapter, an effort to use multilanguage channels was made during the last period as well as to find a way to communicate periodically when a special event needed a particular attention. During 2020 the campaigns related to both MED-GOLD LIVING LAB and Webinar “Timescales of Climate Services for Agriculture” were launched in six languages, after an intensive translation work. *Buffer* (bufferapp.com) was used to schedule tweets three times a day before and during the event. This task was also supported by some Twitter accounts from MED-GOLD partners.

Figure 6-12 shows some examples where the impressions and engagement increase due to promoting MED-GOLD events. According to *Twitter analytics*, during General Assembly promo (Oct-2019 Nov-2019) the number of impressions was 9950, and during MED-GOLD Living Lab, this number was 17817. Following the guidelines described in the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Management Plan [RD1], the majority of posted tweets are at least simple, direct, contain relevant information and include hashtag. In the same way, some advices related to the best time for posting (based on age, occupation, interest) were considered before posting. The strategy adopted consisted of 3 daily Tweets in different language, and rotating the order day by day during the promo period.

The figure displays 12 screenshots of tweets from the @medgold_h2020 account, arranged in a 4x3 grid. Each tweet promotes a different MED-GOLD event or activity, often including photos of participants or speakers. The tweets are in English, Spanish, Greek, and French, demonstrating multilingual communication. Key events mentioned include the General Assembly, the Living Lab, and the École d'été MED-GOLD. The tweets use various social media features like images, video thumbnails, and links to external websites or social media profiles.

Figure 6-12: MED-GOLD Twitter promo

Another issue considered in the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Management Plan [RD1] relates to increasing the number of users to MED-GOLD Twitter account. The goal initially planted for year 2019 was 500 users. Currently the number of MED-GOLD followers is 405 (80% of the initial goal reached).

Although the initial goal is not reached, the outcome is important considering the follower profiles that show interest in the topic that MED-GOLD is spreading: *Climate Services*.

Unfortunately, Twitter Analytics deactivated the “audience” information to analyse the user evolution of the MED-GOLD account. However comparing the number of followers described in the last reported period Summary of Dissemination and Communication Activities N.2 [RD4], the number of followers increased by 106 new followers, which means 36% more compared to the last report.

As was mentioned above, MED-GOLD adopted *Buffer* (bufferapp.com) as a tool to post material in an organized way. The methodology suggests to create a number of tweets two or three weeks before the event, with the scope to prepare and create expectation around the particular topic. These “posts” were then translated to the six MED-GOLD languages (EN, IT, PT, ES, GR, FR) and scheduled to be launched during the promo. The posting times selected were 9:00, 12:00, 15:00 and 19:00 according to Jelen and McCallister [RD7], (2014)

MED-GOLD in YouTube (https://www.YouTube.com/channel/UCnpls45u9oh0uWksh_WCDCw), is another way used to disseminate and communicate the activity of the project. In this specific case, YouTube is not used as a channel but instead is used to store and share the video material prepared for different activities: promo videos, Living Lab sessions and webinars.

6.3.4.MED-GOLD MAILING LISTS

As indicated in the previous report, Summary of Dissemination and Communication Activities N.2 [RD4], and the Milestone MS3 [RD8], the mailing list was created using information collected from European and national organizations. The contacts include relevant stakeholders in the olives/olive oil, grapes/wine, and durum wheat/pasta sectors, as well as those in other agricultural and climate services sectors, which form the base of the MED-GOLD community.

In this reported period the number of contacts has been increased by 12% compared with the previous report; currently 170 contacts mainly related to agriculture and MED-GOLD sectors contribute with the 88% of mailing list contacts (Figure 6.13). This indicates the main interest is focused on the impact of climate on the agriculture and how the climate services support this important sector. Similar to website, the results by country follow a similar behaviour: the Mediterranean countries are the most interested in the project.

Figure 6-13: MED-GOLD Community Mailing List by sector

Additionally, MED-GOLD counts 35 academic networks in different countries: Italy, Spain, France, Portugal, UK and Colombia.

The MED-GOLD community distributed by countries shows the following record: Italy 66, Portugal 45, Spain 19, Greece 13, France 7 India 5, UK 3 and others countries 16.

6.3.5. MED-GOLD NEWSLETTERS

The Newsletters are the way to inform the stakeholders about project results. According to Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Management Plan [RD1], two annual Newsletter must be launched. During this period, two Newsletters were prepared and launched in the frame of communication strategy.

In December 2019, the third Newsletter was available in the MED-GOLD website. The content of this publication focused to inform about the third stage of the project and the advances of the climate service tools. Also some relevant news in the context of the project or similar initiatives were published in this edition. (<https://bit.ly/32QCtlu>)

The fourth Newsletter was published in June 2020 (<https://bit.ly/3bmVHJp>). This edition focused on informing about the test of the climate services tools, activities reached by the second round of deliverables of the sectoral workpackages. Following the trend of the previous Newsletter, the content announced some progress of the project, for example the MED-GOLD dashboard, webinar announcements, etc.

Figure 6.14 shows the general view of the Newsletter published during this period.

Figure 6-14: MED-GOLD Newsletter

According to *Twitter analytics*, the announcement of the Newsletter N° 3 in December 17th had 3020 impressions and had 48 engagements and the Newsletter N°4 had 568 impressions and 41 engagements in July 2nd.

During this reported period, the MED-GOLD media page content (<https://www.med-gold.eu/media/>) which had a total 234 visits.

6.3.6.MED-GOLD EVENTS

The MED-GOLD events are a key piece to communication and dissemination of activities. During this period, some activities were presented remotely due to the Covid-19 crisis, which restricted personal meetings as well as trips. Table 6-5 shows the main events where MED-GOLD participated as organizer or presenter.

Table 6-5 MED-GOLD Events Participation

ID	Name	Role	Date	Location	Type	Attendees
1	Adaptation To Climate Change Of Mediterranean Agriculture	MED-GOLD EVENT	15/10/2019	Cagliari - Italy	Workshop	40
2	On Climate Services As Drivers Of Value Into The Mediterranean Wine Sector	MED-GOLD EVENT	08/01/2020	On line	Webinar	18
3	User Perspective On The Value Of Seasonal Forecasts For Agriculture	MED-GOLD INTERNAL EVENT	11/02/2020	On line	Meeting	
4	What Are The Time Scales Of Climate Services For Agriculture?	MED-GOLD EVENT	21/04/2020	On line	Webinar	90
5	Living Lab 2020: Turning Climate Information Into Value For Traditional Mediterranean Agri-Food Systems.	MED-GOLD EVENT	25/05/2020	On line	Workshop	19
6	European Climate Change Adaption	MED-GOLD ORAL PRESENTATION	28/05/2020	Lisbon - Portugal	Conference	
7	Exploring the added-value of MED-GOLD climate services across crops and agricultural regions	MED-GOLD ORAL PRESENTATION	11/02/2020	Pune - India	Conference	

Into the framework of MED-GOLD sectorial activities, a round of evaluation of MED-GOLD tools was performed and counted with the following participation (Table 6.6) according with the deliverables D2.7 [RD9] and D3.7 [RD10] different professional profiles participated in the evaluation.

Table 6-6 MED-GOLD sectorial evaluation tools

WP	Participant	Sector	Role
WP2	Participant 1	Olive/Oil	Department of supplies and services
WP2	Participant 2	Olive/Oil	Department of olive oil logistics
WP2	Participant 3	Olive/Oil	Department of quality of olive mills
WP2	Participant 4	Olive/Oil	Department of R&D&I
WP2	Participant 5	Olive/Oil	Department of R&D&I
WP2	Participant 6	Olive/Oil	Department of R&D&I
WP3	Participant 1	Grape/Wine	Director of Viticulture Douro
WP3	Participant 2	Grape/Wine	Director of Viticulture
WP3	Participant 3	Grape/Wine	Director of Oenology Douro
WP3	Participant 4	Grape/Wine	Winemaker Douro Superior
WP3	Participant 5	Grape/Wine	Winemaker Douro CimaCorgo
WP3	Participant 6	Grape/Wine	Vineyard Manager Douro
WP3	Participant 7	Grape/Wine	ITC programmer
WP3	Participant 8	Grape/Wine	Vineyard Manager Douro
WP3	Participant 9	Grape/Wine	ITC Manager
WP3	Participant 10	Grape/Wine	Viticulture Support Douro

In the case of WP4 (Durum Wheat /pasta), the evaluation consisted of a series of interactions through email or personal meetings between BARILLA and ENEA, such as indicated the D4.7 [RD11].

6.3.7.INTERACTION WITH OTHER INITIATIVES

As was described in the D.22 [RD4], the synergies with other EU initiatives related to climate, agri-food, and other complementary projects such as Climate-KIC, JPI Climate, FACE-JPI, JPI Water, ERA-NET, have been explored during the project. Among the type of projects, the contacts have been mainly: H2020, Copernicus, ERA4CS, LIFE, JPI, MED, CGIAR.

During the previous period, 14 initiatives related to climate and 9 to agriculture were contracted and 25 potential initiatives were identified [RD4]. In the present period, four extra initiatives were contacted or were identified as potential:

- Africulture: (<http://africultures.eu/>) H2020 project. AfriCultuReS aims to design, implement and demonstrate an integrated agricultural monitoring and early warning system that will support decision making in the field of food security. AfriCultuReS delivers a broad range of climatic, production, biophysical and economic information, for various regions in Africa. They are working in different climate scales. Is a key project in terms of replicability.
- eos4d: (<https://eo4sd.esa.int/>) EO4SD – Earth Observation for Sustainable Development – is a new European Spatial Agency (ESA) initiative which aims to achieve a step increase in the uptake of satellite-based environmental information in the IFIs regional and global programs. It will follow a systematic, userdriven approach in order to meet longer-term, strategic geospatial information needs in the individual developing countries, as well as international and regional development organizations.
- LIFE+Climagri: (<http://www.climagri.eu/index.php/en/>) European Project whose goals are the adaptation of field irrigation crops to climate change. Mitigating the effects of climate change. Designing of agronomic management systems based on Best Management Practices and verifying it by an experimental fields.
- Clúster de CambioClimático: (<https://foretica.org/proyectos-y-soluciones/cluster-de-cambio-climatico/>), is a Spanish cluster. Its goals are: creating roadmaps, collaborating and developing the knowledge according to the effects of climate changes in different sectors in Spain.

6.3.8.EXTERNAL COMMUNICATION CHANNELS

The participation of partners has also contributed to the communication of the MED-GOLD activities using their own communication channels as well as participating in local radio and television broadcasts. Figure 6.15 summarizes the participation of external sources of communication during the reported period. A complete table is available in the WP6 repository (<https://bit.ly/3jYhQRd>). The external media channels contribute by 35% and the publication of news in external websites contributes by with 25% in the MED-GOLD communication. The different ways used to engage the users and keep the activity around MED-GOLD is also worth noticing.

Figure 6-15: MED-GOLD Communication Activity

6.3.9. MED-GOLD LIVING LAB

Initially this activity called MED-GOLD summer school was scheduled to take place in Cagliari (Italy) during May 2020, however due to the worldwide Covid-19 crisis, the project adopted online methods to reach the objective initially planted. As mentioned previously, an intense campaign in different languages was launched few weeks prior to the new event, which took place during May 2020.

This event counted the participation of 19 students mainly from Italy, Spain, Netherlands and Germany. This Living Lab is currently available in the MED-GOLD YouTube channel as well as MED-GOLD website (<https://www.med-gold.eu/med-gold-living-lab-2020/>). According to google analytics this page have a total of 506 visits since April 2020. Figure 6.16 shows a snapshot of session 4 where the MED-GOLD dashboard is being explained. Some of the actions proposed in the C&D activities are to use the recorded videos of the MED-GOLD Living Lab as media content to continue the dissemination purposes.

Figure 6-16: MED-GOLD Living Lab

6.3.10. MED-GOLD INFOSHEET

Three infosheets have been published during this period, meaning a total of six publications since MED-GOLD project has started. The most recent publications are:

- **Climate services for the coffee sector** (https://www.med-gold.eu/wp-content/uploads/docs/MED-GOLD_infosheet04_coffee-EN.pdf), oriented to coffee and mainly shows how the climate services help to optimize both the long term strategy and the shorter term agricultural crop management.
- **Time scales for climate services** (https://www.med-gold.eu/wp-content/uploads/docs/MED-GOLD_infosheet05_timescales-EN.pdf), this infosheet explains and clarifies the differences between the time scales concepts involved in the project.
- **Climate predictions for agriculture**, focused on explaining how the climate predictions provide information for a specific period of time. For example, months (or seasons, years or decades) will be more, equal or less warm than normal.

Following the strategy adopted in MED-GOLD, each infosheet is available in the website, translated in 6 languages and promoted in the social networks channel. Figure 6-17 shows a general view of the three infosheets in FR, ES and EN, respectively.

According to google analytics, the publications section has received 500 visits during this period.

Turning climate-related information into added value for traditional MEDiterranean Grape, Olive and Durum wheat food systems Grant Agreement n° 776467

SERVICES CLIMATOLOGIQUES POUR LE SECTEUR BLE DUR ET PÂTES

"Face face au changement climatique est l'un des plus grands défis de notre époque" Olivier Monin, Institut National de la Recherche Agronomique (INRA)

Le blé dur et, par conséquent, la production des pâtes sont influencés par les conditions météorologiques et climatiques et sont fortement affectés par les variations climatiques. Par conséquent, la fiabilité et son expansion ainsi que les stratégies potentielles d'adaptation dans des conditions climatiques changeantes doivent être évaluées. MED-GOLD collabore avec des services agro-climatologiques fournissant des informations climatiques à moyen (3-11 mois) et à long terme (20-30 ans). Pour fournir le plus haut niveau à la prise de décision, les services sont co-développés avec des utilisateurs professionnels du secteur.

Les producteurs de blé dur font face à divers défis qui affectent plusieurs processus des décisions dans leurs activités, tels que la gestion agricole, la gestion des stocks et les décisions stratégiques. Certains exemples sont présentés en dessous pour montrer comment les services climatologiques - dans ce cas, les prévisions des variables climatiques et d'indices bioclimatiques - peuvent appuyer des décisions cruciales tout au long de la chaîne alimentaire du blé dur et soutenir les défis posés par la variabilité et le changement climatique.

Échelle de temps	Type de données	Donnée	Services climatologiques (MED-GOLD)	Avantages
Temps court (de 1 à 11 mois)	Agro-météo	Méthodes personnalisées de travail du sol, fertilisation, irrigation préventive et gestion des mauvaises herbes	Développement phénologique du blé Température Précipitations Équilibre hydrique	Minimiser l'exposition aux conditions météorologiques extrêmes Réduction des coûts grâce à une planification optimale de la fertilisation et de la gestion agricole
		Plus hautes précipitations avec la variabilité et le séchage de la récolte	Pluies plus en phase Plus d'azote pour l'augmentation de l'azote	Maximiser le rendement et la qualité des cultures Optimiser l'utilisation d'engrais
Sécheresse de stocks	Sécheresse de stocks	Méthodes contractées et prix	Indice de risque de gel Indice de stress hydrique	Meilleure planification de la chaîne d'approvisionnement, des contrats et des prix
		Meilleure planification de la chaîne d'approvisionnement	Indice de risque de gel Indice de stress hydrique	Meilleure planification de la chaîne d'approvisionnement, des contrats et des prix
Temps long (au-delà de 11 mois)	Stratégie à long terme	Sélection des futures nouvelles zones de culture	Changements potentiels de rendement Risque accru de sécheresse Changements climatiques extrêmes (vagues de chaleur, sécheresses, inondations, incendies, etc.)	Meilleure estimation de la production pour le marché et la sécurité alimentaire Risque accru de sécheresse Changements climatiques extrêmes (vagues de chaleur, sécheresses, inondations, incendies, etc.)
		Changements climatiques extrêmes (vagues de chaleur, sécheresses, inondations, incendies, etc.)	Changements potentiels de rendement Risque accru de sécheresse Changements climatiques extrêmes (vagues de chaleur, sécheresses, inondations, incendies, etc.)	Meilleure estimation de la production pour le marché et la sécurité alimentaire Risque accru de sécheresse Changements climatiques extrêmes (vagues de chaleur, sécheresses, inondations, incendies, etc.)

ESCALAS TEMPORALES DE LOS SERVICIOS CLIMÁTICOS PARA AGRICULTURA

Las predicciones pueden dividirse en diferentes categorías de acuerdo a escalas temporales: predicciones del pasado, predicciones meteorológicas, predicciones climáticas y proyecciones climáticas, cada una entendida desde el punto de vista del futuro. Una clara comprensión de las diferencias entre esas escalas de tiempo ayuda a entender cómo esta información puede servir de apoyo a determinadas decisiones que necesitan ser tomadas sobre el terreno.

DECISION (1-11 months): Meteorological forecasts, weather forecasts, crop growth models, soil moisture models, etc.

PROYECCIONES DEL PASADO (1-11 months): Historical climate data, crop yield trends, etc.

PROYECCIONES CLIMÁTICAS (1-11 months): Climate forecasts, crop yield forecasts, etc.

PROYECCIONES CLIMÁTICAS (10-30 years): Climate projections, crop yield projections, etc.

PROYECCIONES CLIMÁTICAS (10-30 years): Climate projections, crop yield projections, etc.

CLIMATE PREDICTIONS FOR AGRICULTURE

A frequently-used approach to compare near-future climate conditions consists of taking the historical average (i.e. average of observations) for the 20-30 years for a specific climate variable (over a fixed area of interest). For example, we would assume that the mean temperature for that summer in a specific region would equal the average temperature (averaged along summer months) in the past 20-30 years. However, this approach would be flawed as it is based on the historical average. Instead, they can use a different approach, which relies on the average (mean) conditions of the most recent past (i.e. the last 10-20 years). Such approaches (the historical average and the climate memory average) assume that future conditions will be similar to past conditions, which has been shown to be highly variable, meaning that new year can be statistically different from the previous one. Similarly, these approaches cannot predict events that have not occurred before, such as extreme events, which are becoming more frequent under the context of climate change.

Climate predictions provide information on how likely it is that the coming months (or seasons, years or decades) will be more, equal or less warm (or wet or windy, etc.) than normal in the area. Normal refers to the historical average for a particular climate variable. This is based on the long-term average of the historical observations (see Fig. 1).

HOW TO INTERPRET CLIMATE PREDICTIONS

Climate predictions are probabilities. They give information on the probability of certain outcomes to occur (e.g. that the temperature in the next month will be higher than normal) in a region in the South of Spain. The climate prediction will be higher than normal (or lower than normal) if the probability is higher (or lower) than the historical average. The model outputs are based on the historical average, which were compared to locations where the probability prediction is higher than normal. The model outputs are based on the historical average, which were compared to locations where the probability prediction is higher than normal. The model outputs are based on the historical average, which were compared to locations where the probability prediction is higher than normal.

Figure 6-17: MED-GOLD Infosheets

6.3.11. MED-GOLD WEBINAR

Two webinars took place during this period and focused on the Mediterranean wine sector and the time scale of climate.

- **Climate services as drivers of value into the Mediterranean wine sector:** imparted on January 8, this webinar discussed how climate services can help the wine sector cope with climate change and create opportunities. This webinar counted 18 participants and was imparted in Portuguese
- **What are the time scales of climate services for agriculture?:** took place on April 21. In this webinar researchers and users from each sector explained the difference between the time scales of climate services for agriculture, including weather forecasts, seasonal predictions, decadal predictions and climate change projections. This webinar counted 90 participants and was imparted in English. Figure 6.18 shows a snapshot of the presentation.

WHAT ARE THE TIME SCALES OF CLIMATE SERVICES FOR AGRICULTURE?

TUESDAY 21 APRIL 2020
THE WEBINAR WILL START AT 12:30H CEST

Climate projections

Climate projections are simulations of Earth's climate in future decades (typically until 2100) obtained by running numerical models which may cover either the entire globe or a specific region e.g. Europe. These models are referred to as Global Climate Models (GCMs) or Regional Climate Models (RCMs), respectively.

Climate models are imperfect representations of the climate system and different models respond differently to the same climate forcing agents.

Figure 6-18: MED-GOLD Webinar

6.3.12. MED-GOLD FORUM

MED-GOLD forum is oriented mainly to keep contact with the MED-GOLD community and discuss open topics such as the result of events like webinars, schools, workshops, etc. During this period despite the high

number of participants, the forum activity was open after the webinar: what are the time scales of climate services for agriculture? During April, this forum counted the visit of 33 participants. Figure 6.19 shows the MED-GOLD forum activity after the webinar presentation.

Figure 6-19: MED-GOLD Forum

6.3.13. MED-GOLD PUBLICATIONS

The dissemination of the MED-GOLD outcomes, advances, and its applications has been shared to the public through different ways. During 2019-2020, 14 abstracts were submitted by sector partners, 8 articles were published in peer-reviewed publications and 2 are currently under review. In total 21 actions are referenced to the dissemination of results in MED-GOLD. Table 6.7 summarizes the actions.

Table 6-7 MED-GOLD Publications Actions

No	Title	Type of publication/event	Status	Year	Sector
1	Yield prediction of durum wheat: the added value of MED-GOLD climate services products	22nd European Geosciences Union General Assembly	Abstract submitted	2020	Durum wheat
2	Turn climate information into value for the Mediterranean wine sector: the MED-GOLD potential	22nd European Geosciences Union General Assembly	Abstract submitted	2020	Wine
3	What light is available for understory crops under high-density and super-high-density olive orchards? Spatial and temporal patterns of transmitted PAR	5th European Agroforestry Conference	Abstract submitted	2020	Olive
4	Exploring the added - value of MED-GOLD climate services across crops and agricultural regions.	Conference	Abstract submitted	2020	Climate
5	Development of climate services from the user perspective: the MED-GOLD experience.	European Meteorological Society Annual Meeting	Abstract submitted	2019	Climate
6	The MED-GOLD project: Advanced user-centric climate services for higher resilience and profitability in the grape and wine sector.	Journal article	Published	2019	Climate
7	Resiliência e adaptação: uso de informação histórica para prever a qualidade de uvas e vinhos numa determinada propriedade da Região Demarcada do Douro	Journal article	Published	2019	Wine

No	Title	Type of publication/event	Status	Year	Sector
8	Global pest invasions: why correlative risk assessment may be wrong	Journal article	Abstract submitted	2020	Agriculture
9	Modelling light below tree canopies overestimates net photosynthesis and radiation use efficiency in understory crops by averaging light in space and time	Journal article	Abstract submitted	2020	Climate
10	The Risk of Unprecedented Rainfall in Wine Regions of Northern Portugal	Journal article	Abstract submitted	2020	Wine
11	The Influence of Climate on Agricultural Decisions for Three European Crops: A Systematic Review	Journal article	Published	2020	Agriculture
12	Estimating resilience of crop production systems: From theory to practice	Journal article	Published	2020	Agriculture
13	Thermal biology of <i>Tutaabsoluta</i> : demographic parameters and facultative diapause	Journal article	Published	2020	Agriculture
14	Time-varying impact of climate on maize and wheat yields in France since 1900.	Journal article	Published	2020	Climate
15	The coffee agroecosystem: bio-economic analysis of coffee berry borer control (<i>Hypothenemushampei</i>).	Journal article	Published	2020	Coffee
16	Performance of seasonal forecasts of Douro and Port wine production.	Journal article	Published	2020	Wine
17	Extreme rainfall in the Douro Valley.	Journal article	Under Review	2020	Climate
18	Engagement, involvement and empowerment: three realms of a co-production framework for climate services	Journal article	Under Review	2020	Climate
19	Intercepted PAR and spatial and temporal distribution of transmitted PAR under high density and super high-density olive (<i>Olea europaea</i> L.) orchards. Trees	Journal article	Abstract submitted		Olive
20	MED-GOLD Living Lab 2020: the story of an online training event	Online training event	Abstract submitted	2020	Climate
21	Turning climate data into value for productive activities in the user's perspective.	Seventh Annual Conference of the Italian Society for Climate Sciences (SISC)	Abstract submitted	2019	Climate

6.3.14. CONTACT WITH THE POLICY COMMUNITY

The continue interaction with the policy community is a relevant process considering that MED-GOLD aims to support policy making. As described in D6.22 [RD.4] , the MED-GOLD strategy for engaging the policy community defines both short-term and long-term actions informing the policy community about the project and its relevance to the agriculture sector and getting informed/receive feedback about the policy needs regarding climate information and services. Along of this reported period (Nov 2019 – Oct 2020) 4 interactions with the policy community were performed, increasing the number of interactions in 50% compared with the last period.

The engagement activities focused to policy community reached the following results:

1. MED-GOLD Partner: BSC
 - a. Date: 30/01/2020
 - b. Type of interaction: Presentation on climate services at the Energy Platforms Policy Dialogue
2. MED-GOLD Partner: BSC
 - a. Date: 28/012020
 - b. Type of interaction: Suggestions for agriculture topic proposal for future PRIMA Call
3. MED-GOLD Partner: SOGRAPE
 - a. Date: 16/10/2020

- b. Type of interaction: Organization of presentation about the Copernicus Climate Change Service and how its tools are relevant for grape and wine production.
 - c. Main Discussion: This presentation was addressed: (i) climate change, (ii) management of climate big data by Copernicus and (iii) quality control of climate information provided. He provided insights on the datasets, tools and applications offered by Copernicus for the wine sector and highlighted MED-GOLD as a research project meant to provide answers to specific challenges of the grape and wine sector. As a result, the OIV is considering to create a global climate atlas of wine regions that could be hosted in the COPERNICUS system and benefit from MED-GOLD tools such as the dashboard.
4. MED-GOLD Partner: ENEA / EC2CE
- a. Date: This meeting is scheduled to December 2020
 - b. Type of Interaction: Attended the MED-GOLD participatory workshop in Antequera. Contribution in the design of Olivia tool [RD9]. They will attend the European Workshop on Climate Services/Policy event planned for 02 Dec 2020.

Currently, 5 organizations of the policy community have been contacted without getting a response, however can be considered as potential interactions for the future. In this perspective, the policy event planned for 02 dec 2020, 'Climate services for a climate-resilient Europe - Climate services for a climate-resilient Europe Success stories, lessons learnt and remaining challenges' that MED-GOLD team supported to organize could be an excellent further opportunity to interact with policy community [RD12].

6.3.15. SUMMARY OF THE THIRD REPORTING PERIOD

The main results of the reported period are presented in a qualitative way according to the impact measured through the website and social media analysis. The website had an increasing trend (based on the number of visitors), where the multilanguage content and the consolidated design (fronted) played a relevant role to the publication of dissemination material like infosheet and newsletter. In addition, although the goal proposed has not been reached yet, the social media channel increased the number of users, impressions and engagements compared to the previous reported periods.

The alternative ways to website as a mean of communications were the social media, YouTube channel and external communication channels (Twitter, LinkedIn, websites, radio, TV, etc), which enhanced interest in the MED-GOLD project.

The intensive work performed since the second General Assembly (Oct-2019), and the capacity to perform dissemination work like the Living Lab have been key in to reach the goal.

Some of the numbers reached during the third reporting period are summarized in Table 6.8

Table 6-8 MED-GOLD Activity results from P2 (Nov 2019 - Oct 2020)

Activity	Measure
MED-GOLD WEBSITE	
Website Users	3432
Number website Sessions	4510
Number Page Views	11147
Bounce Rate	61.33%
Average Session Duration	0:02
Number of sessions per user	1.81
Pages/Session	2.47
MED-GOLD SOCIAL NETWORKS	
Number Twitter impressions	124262
Number Twitter engagements	2234

Activity	Measure
Number Twitter retweets	349
Number Twitter likes	578
Number Twitter media views	
Number Twitter URL clicks	412
Twitter engagement rate	4.70%
MED-GOLD MAILING LISTS	
Member increasing rate	12%
Number of Academic Network	35
MED-GOLD NEWSLETTERS	
Total number of published Newsletter	2
MED-GOLD EVENTS	
Conferences participations	2
Number of workshops (participation and imparted)	5
INTERACTION WITH OTHER INITIATIVES	
New Interactions	4
EXTERNAL COMMUNICATION CHANNELS	
External media channels contribution increasing rate	35%
Publication of news in external websites contribution increasing rate	25%
DISSEMINATION CHANNELS	
MED-GOLD Living Lab	1
MED-GOLD Infosheet	3
MED-GOLD Webinar	1
New MED-GOLD Forum Opened Discussions	31
MED-GOLD Publications	
Papers	8
Article Under review	2
Abstracts Submitted	11
CONTACT WITH THE POLICY COMMUNITY	
Contacted members	4

Finally, the end of this reported period coincided with the General Assembly 2020, which took place on-line between October 19th and October 21st. Some of the most relevant conclusions related to Dissemination and Communication activities were focused on reinforcing the social media strategies, improve the glossary (website and dashboard) and to take advantage of the material used in the assembly to be published in the various available communication channels.

7. EXPLOITATION OF RESULTS

All activities and outcomes described in the previous chapter can be used in the frame of the tasks of WP5 and WP6 mainly, but not exclusively; dissemination and communication imply necessary support of other MED-GOLD workpackages too.

The presented results constitute the most representative and effective way to consolidate or redefine the strategies adopted during this period to engage the public (general, stakeholders, academic and scientific community, etc.) to participate in the MED-GOLD project.

END OF DOCUMENT

